

Comparative effects of basal broadcast urea (BU), split urea (SU), supergranules (SG) of urea placed at 10-cm depth, basal broadcast sulfur-coated urea (SCU), and sulfur-coated supergranules of urea (SCSG) placed at 10cm depth on growth and nitrogen recovery by IR38 in the greenhouse.

Fertilizer ^a	Panicles (no.)	Dry matter (g/pot)		Apparent nitrogen recovery ^b (%)
		Grain	Total tops	
O	27	33	99	—
BU	31	38	123	28
SU	31	41	134	48
SG	31	45	151	69
SCU	34	46	140	56
SCSG	39	52	163	89

^aAll fertilizers were applied at the rate of 460 mg N/pot.

^bApparent N recovery = $\frac{\text{N uptake in fertilized plant} - \text{N uptake in control (mg)}}{460 \text{ mg}} \times 100\%$.

practical means of achieving such combination was provided by the

Fertilizer Technology Division of the International Fertilizer Development

Center (IFDC) in the form of sulfur-coated urea supergranules. Preliminary results obtained with this experimental material in a greenhouse study at IFDC headquarters in Alabama are reported here.

The table shows the mean data from two soils and two water regimes (which had only minor effects on rice growth). The results suggest that the combination of deep placement and slow release shows considerable promise for improving fertilizer efficiency.

The sulfur-coated supergranules of urea are being tested at IRRI in 1978 as part of a joint IRRI-IFDC project aimed at improving nitrogen fertilizer efficiency for rice.

Environment and its influence

Possible causes of a new physiological disorder of rice in Korea

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New varieties derived from indica/japonica crosses have been successfully grown in the Republic of Korea. These short, lodging-resistant, and high-tillering varieties are now planted on 660,000 ha, about half of Korea's total rice land. Consequently, the national average rice yield in Korea reached 6.64 t/ha, the world's highest, in 1977.

Yushin, one of the best indica/japonica varieties, has many good characteristics and gives high yields under favorable weather and soil conditions. But in 1976, it suffered *sudden wilting* in farmers' fields while other varieties such as Tongil seemed healthy under similar or identical conditions. Subsequent investigations into this new physiological disorder suggested that low sunlight, excessive nitrogen application, and highly reductive soil conditions either singly or combined, might be possible causes of the disorder.

Some visual symptoms of *sudden wilting* are orange discoloration of leaves,

development of nodal roots above the soil surface, total root rot, and lodging. Those observations led to the hypothesis that suffocation of root tissues was a direct cause of the disorder.

The oxygen transport characteristics of Yushin, Tongil, and IR262 were examined by two methods. First, the number and size of the air spaces in each internode were investigated (see table). In the 5th internode from the top, all three varieties have a similar number of air spaces, although the air spaces of Tongil were larger. In the 4th internode, Tongil had 31 air spaces, Yushin had only 2, and one of Tongil's parents, IR262, had none. The observations indicated that the ability of Yushin and IR262 for oxygen transport is very limited compared with that of Tongil.

Second, soil-cultured plants of the three varieties were subjected to paraffin treatment. To decrease the oxygen supply from the air to root tissues through the soil-water system, a layer of liquid paraffin about 5 to 6 mm thick was applied to the water surface in the pots at 47 days after seeding. The experiment was repeated twice. Each time *sudden wilting* was observed on Yushin and IR262 at about 1 week after

the treatment, but Tongil remained green and healthy.

The findings suggest that Yushin has limited ability to transport oxygen. The limited oxygen supply may cause suffocation of root tissues, weaken metabolic activity of the tissues, and induce root rot, subsequently inducing *sudden wilting* and lodging under

Varietal difference in number and size of air spaces in the internodes of rice plants at the ripening stage. IRRI, 1978.

Internode position ^a	Air spaces	
	No.	Mean diameter (mm)
	<i>Tongil</i>	
3d	0	—
4th	31	0.15
5th	31	0.31
	<i>Yushin</i>	
3d	0	—
4th	2	—
5th	29	0.24
	<i>IR262</i>	
3d	0	—
4th	0	—
5th	31	0.24

^aFrom top of plant.

Provisional mechanism for *sudden wilting* of the rice variety Yushin.

unfavorable weather and soil conditions. We describe a provisional mechanism for *sudden wilting* of Yushin in the figure. Further investigations into air space and

oxygen transport ability of rice varieties are under way. They may throw light on varietal differences in tolerance for some known physiological disorders. ❧

When sprayed at the seedling stage, both Bzi and zinc sulfate were ineffective on NC1281 but increased yield in Jaya (see table). The two chemicals significantly increased yield components as well as yield per plant in both varieties when they were sprayed at preflowering and postflowering stages. The effect was greatest when the chemicals were applied at a later stage of growth. Plant growth was found related directly to yield. Sprayed at the preflowering stage, both Bzi and zinc sulfate were more effective in increasing yield in NC1281 than in Jaya; when sprayed at postflowering the two chemicals were equally effective in increasing the yield parameters of both varieties. Higher yield at the later stages might be due to efficient preflowering translocation as shown by the higher grain:straw ratio.

The two chemicals did not increase seed protein content; however, a slight increase in protein content was observed in Jaya sprayed with Bzi at preflowering stage. ❧

Increased productivity in tall and dwarf rice varieties through benzimidazole and zinc sulfate sprays

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We previously reported that spraying Jaya rice with cytokinins and zinc salt ($ZnSO_4$) at a particular developmental stage was effective in increasing yield. In this experiment, the effectiveness of benzimidazole (Bzi) and zinc sulfate as foliar sprays was observed on yield and yield components of the photoperiod-sensitive tall rice variety NC1281 and the photoperiod-insensitive dwarf Jaya. Aqueous solutions (100 $\mu g/ml$) of Bzi and zinc sulfate were sprayed on the rice plant at seedling, preflowering, and postflowering stages. The growth and yield parameters considered were plant height, straw weight, number of panicles, percentage of ripened grains, grain:straw ratio, yield per plant, and protein content of the seeds.

Effect of benzimidazole and zinc on some yield parameters of tall (NC1281) and dwarf (Jaya) rice varieties, West Bengal, India.

Variety	Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Straw wt (g/plant)	Yield parameters at harvest				
				Panicles (no./plant)	Grain wt (no./plant)	Grain:straw ratio	Ripened grains (%)	Protein content (mg/g)
<i>Seedling stage (48 days old)</i>								
NC1281	Bzi	146.5	74.4	10.2	23.1	0.311	89.4	75.3
	Zn	145.4	63.4	8.8	23.5	0.370	90.6	74.1
Jaya	Bzi	89.0	32.0	10.0	18.3	0.572	72.9	79.0
	Zn	85.8	30.8	13.4	21.5	0.699	65.4	86.6
<i>Preflowering stage (80 days old)</i>								
NC1281	Bzi	152.6	81.8	10.0	27.8	0.340	93.3	74.8
	Zn	146.6	81.0	12.2	28.7	0.353	90.2	80.6
Jaya	Bzi	94.6	48.4	10.8	19.3	0.396	69.8	91.4
	Zn	92.7	42.7	10.0	16.5	0.306	67.9	84.6
<i>Postflowering stage (96 days old)</i>								
NC1281	Bzi	147.0	78.2	11.4	28.4	0.363	91.6	80.6
	Zn	144.8	76.4	14.2	31.4	0.401	89.6	80.6
Jaya	Bzi	94.3	51.0	11.2	20.9	0.410	74.0	85.0
	Zn	90.8	46.0	15.6	23.2	0.504	69.6	85.5
<i>Control</i>								
NC1281		149.6	76.4	10.6	24.0	0.314	91.8	90.7
Jaya		92.2	40.6	10.0	16.2	0.398	70.4	84.6